

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D7.5: Report on bio-chemical characterization of biomass extracts and pure compounds

REPORTING PERIOD	
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RM7 Responsible	Stefano Superchi

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Table 1 - List of Deliverables

NUM	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE*	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL **	DUE DATE
D7.1	Data on type, quality, availability, and geographical distribution of agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report and a database on distribution and availability of biomass suitable for valorization	UNIBAS	PU	M12
D7.2	Delivery of validated extraction protocols according to the treated biomass type	R	Report on validated methodologies for value-added extracts depending on biomass type	UNIBAS	PU	M22
D7.3	Extracts and pure compounds suitable for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.4	Extracts suitable as biopesticides	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.5	Report on bio-chemical characterization of biomass extracts and pure compounds	R		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.6	Biomaterials for bioactive extracts delivery	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.8	Formulates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications (in collaboration with companies)	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.9	Formulates for agro-chemical applications (in collaboration with companies)	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.10	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report on validated methodologies suitable for scale-up and industrial production	UNIBAS	PU	M30

Table 2 - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
M7.1	Survey on regional scale of the type, quality, availability, distribution of biomass from agro-forest waste	7	8	Report
M7.2	Selection of biomass materials suitable for valorization (at least three)	7	10	Report
M7.3	Validation of extraction protocols for selected matrices and materials	7	12	Report
M7.4	Availability of biomass extracts (at least five) suitable for bio-activity tests	7	16	Material
M7.5	Production of a report on bioactivity of different materials and compounds	7	20	Report
M7.6	Availability of biomaterials for bioactive material delivery	7	26	Material
M7.8	Availability of formulates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications	7	28	Material
M7.9	Availability of formulates for agro-chemical applications	7	28	Material
M7.10	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	7	30	Report

INTRODUCTION

As reported in the Deliverable 7.3 report, our research work was particularly focused on recovery of bioactive materials from grape pomace and pomegranate waste.

The investigation on the extraction techniques allowed to identify, for both biomasses, the most suitable extraction methods, taking into account the extraction performances and selectivity, the practicality and economy of the process, its environmental impact and its possible application on industrial scale.

On the basis of these parameters the extracts coming from digestion process (DIG) of grape pomace and the extracts in ethanol, 2-MeTHF, and DMC of pomegranate waste were selected for the subsequent assays on the biological activity.

1. Bioactivity tests on selected biomass extracts

1.1 Bioactivity tests on extract from grape pomace waste.

1.1.1 Anti-proliferative activity evaluation

A growing number of investigations identified specialized molecules from plant and their by-products as agents able to induce cell apoptosis, thereby playing a crucial role in clearing mutated hyperproliferating cells. It was demonstrated that phenols may exert anti-proliferative and antineoplastic activities by influencing differentiation, proliferation, and apoptosis in various cancer cells. Specifically, active compounds from grape pomace, like anthocyanidins and flavonoids, demonstrated proapoptotic and growth inhibition effects on different cancer cell lines. However, as far as is known, no study reported the potential activity of Aglianico grape pomace on hepatocarcinoma cell lines. For this reason, once the extracts' antioxidant activity and presence of tannins, flavonoids, and anthocyanins were validated, the Aglianico grape pomace activity was investigated on either IHH hepatic cells or HepG2 cancer cells.

All of the extracts examined reduced the viability of HepG2 cells in a dose-dependent manner at 24 and 48 h (Fig. 1). B DIG and T DIG were the most active extracts after 24 h (IC_{50} of $58.72 \pm 5.88 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and $98.75 \pm 8.27 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively) and 48 h (IC_{50} of $49.40 \pm 6.20 \mu\text{g/mL}$ and $63.04 \pm 4.54 \mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively), thus confirming spectrophotometric assay since these extracts showed the highest amount of flavonoids and anthocyanins. This cytotoxic activity may be due to the ability of Aglianico grape pomace phenols to affect proliferation and apoptosis in cancer cells. A previous investigation on

gastrointestinal digested Aglianico grape pomace extract, indeed, demonstrated that this by-product might determine a significant increase of the proapoptotic marker Bax and reduction in the anti-apoptotic marker Bcl-2 in HT29 and SW480 cells, thereby inducing the mitochondrial apoptotic pathway.

Fig. 1. Cell viability on immortalized liver cancer cell line HepG2 treated with different concentrations (10–500 µg/mL) Aglianico Grape of **A-D**) Barile (B), **B-E**) Torrecuso (T), and **C-F**) Cantine del Notaio (CNS) hydroalcoholic extracts. DIG, digestion; ASE, accelerated solvent extraction.

Aglianico grape pomace extracts were also evaluated for their effect on nontumor cells IHH, showing no cytotoxic activity. This is an essential aspect and reflects the nature of phenols, which can exert a differential activity by targeting cancer cells but not normal ones. As in the present investigation, a recent study indeed demonstrated that grape pomace extracts rich in polyphenols, mainly anthocyanins, was cytotoxic in hepatocarcinoma cells but not in human non-cancer fibroblasts.

1.1.2 Effect on intracellular ROS

It is known that phenols have distinct mechanisms for regulating the cells' redox potential depending on their antioxidant and pro-oxidant activities. When exerting antioxidant action, phenols act through three different mechanisms: induction of the antioxidant defense system, scavenging oxidants, and transition metals complexation. In contrast, polyphenols' pro-oxidant activities are mainly investigated for use in the anti-cancer fields and are supported by their capacity to produce phenoxyl radicals or ROS upon exposure to transition metals. Thanks to this double activity, phenols may induce

healthy cells' mitogenesis or aberrant cells' mitophagy by activating or inactivating the PKD/NF- κ B pathway. Considering this background, the most cytotoxic Aglianico grape pomace extracts (B DIG and T DIG) were investigated for their effect on intracellular ROS in hepatocarcinoma HepG2 cells. Therefore, HepG2 cells were exposed to B DIG and T DIG extracts (10–500 μ g/mL) for 24 h and 48 h with different concentrations, observing a dose-dependent increase in ROS levels (Fig. 2). B DIG extract, in particular, showed the greatest pro-oxidant effect. This increase in oxidative stress might be one of the possible mechanisms that underwent the demonstrated anti- proliferative effects. These findings align with previous investigations demonstrating that either extracts from red or white grape pomace induce cytotoxic effects by generating ROS, leading to caspase activation and apoptosis. The pro-oxidant effect of grape pomace may be related to the presence of terpenes and flavonoids since they can trigger oxidative stress and DNA damage in cancer cells, thereby activating the cells' apoptosis machinery.

Fig. 2. ROS levels were determined in HepG2 cells treated for 24 h and 48 h with **A**) Barile (B) and **B**) Torrecuso (T) extract obtained by hydroalcoholic digestion (DIG). Results are presented as the mean \pm standard deviation of three independent experiments ($n = 3$). ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$, vs Control (CTRL). NAC, acetyl-L-cysteine.

1.2 Bioactivity tests on extract from pomegranate waste.

The bioactivity of the crude pomegranate ethanolic extract and of the DES fractions was tested. The investigation was centered on the possible effect of the extract on macrophage activation and inflammatory response including the role of immunometabolism modulator. Therefore, the

ethanolic crude extract was first tested for the effect on cell proliferation both on human macrophages and on macrophages obtained from the U937 cell line.

Table 1. Flavonoids and phenolic acids found in pomegranate waste extract (PWE). Values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

Flavonoid	mg/g	Phenolic Acids	mg/g
Baicalein	0.04 \pm 0.005	Ellagic acid dihydrate	1.18 \pm 0.03
(-)-Epigallocatechin gallate hydrate	0.19 \pm 0.005	Gallic acid	0.08 \pm 0.004
Baicalin	0.01 \pm 0.005		
Apigenin	0.04 \pm 0.005		
Rutin hydrate	0.02 \pm 0.005		
Phloridzin	0.05 \pm 0.005		

The characterization of the Pomegranate Waste Extract (PWE) in macrophage activation and inflammatory response, and the secretion of proinflammatory cytokines has been evaluated both in U937 cell line and in macrophages differentiated from PBMCs. In both experimental models, macrophages were activated by *E. coli* lipopolysaccharide (LPS). The secretion of IL-1 beta, IL-6 and IL-8 proinflammatory cytokines was significantly affected by PWE treatment. As a control, the secretion of the cytokine IL-10 was also quantified under the same experimental conditions. All cytokines were evaluated by specific ELISA assays performed by using the cell culture medium. Since in recent years it has been demonstrated that there is a metabolic reprogramming involved in driving the function of macrophages and consequently the cellular phenotype during the inflammatory response, an assessment of immunometabolic parameters is underway.

These analyses will allow us to better understand the molecular mechanism underlying the effects observed so far in LPS-induced macrophages upon PWE treatment. In this context, after observing a PWE effect on the enzymatic activity of the glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH – encoded by *GLUD1* human gene) which catalyzes the reversible conversion of glutamate to α -ketoglutarate and ammonia, we also found a reduction of GDH protein content in LPS-induced macrophages treated with PWE. Through western blotting experiments, other immunometabolic enzymes have been investigated. Among them, a well-defined result is related to the malic enzyme isoform 1 (ME1), a cytosolic protein which catalyzes the reversible oxidative decarboxylation of L-malate into pyruvate and CO₂ with the reduction of NADP⁺ to NADPH in the presence of a divalent metal ion, Mn²⁺ or Mg²⁺. It is worth noting that NADPH is a substrate for both inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) and NADPH oxidase (NOX), involved in the synthesis of nitric oxide (NO) and ROS inflammatory mediators, respectively. Therefore, by

balancing NADPH, ME1 has been described as a crucial metabolic enzyme in proinflammatory activated macrophages. Interestingly, in previous studies we have shown that both human *GLUD1* and *ME1* genes are transcriptionally regulated by the transcription factor NF- κ B in LPS-activated macrophages. Since in the previous months we have demonstrated that PWE affects NF- κ B in activated macrophages, it is likely that PWE works through this transcriptional factor in regulating both *GLUD1* and *ME1* genes. The evaluation of the enzymatic activity of ME1 under the same experimental conditions is ongoing. In the meantime, other enzymes of immunometabolism as well as other transcriptional factors linked to the metabolic reprogramming of activated macrophages are being screened.

PWE has also been tested on liver cancer cells. We chose liver cancer because it is one of the most fatal cancers very often diagnosed in more advanced stages with unfavorable diagnosis and poor prognosis. At present, no effective and specific targeted treatment options exist for patients. Automatic cell counting and clonogenic assay highlighted PWE's ability to reduce cell viability even at concentrations less than 10 μ g/mL. Both non-tumor liver cells and PBMCs isolated from healthy donors were used as control cells. In Figure 1A is reported the effect of PWE on CCLP1 cancer cells, while in Figure 1B the effect on control cells. Noteworthy, up to 96 hours, PWE treatment had little or no effect on growth rate of control cells. Therefore, these findings suggest a specific effect of PWE in decreasing cell proliferation in liver cancer cells only.

Figure 1. PWE inhibits viability of CCLP1 cells.

Cell proliferation has been assessed by both automatic cell counter and CellTiter-Glo[®] 2.0 Cell Viability Assay. This effect has also been evaluated in 3D spheroidal cultures, thus strengthening the data obtained in 2D cell cultures from different cell lines. Interestingly, PWE treatment of spheroids was able to induce morphological alterations of the 3D structure. Moreover, the wound-healing assay (also known as a scratch assay) revealed that PWE reduced liver cancer cell migration. This process has been monitored for 96 hours by microscopy and acquiring images every day. All these experiments were performed with different concentrations of PWE in order to find the optimal concentration range. Since metabolic reprogramming is a major hallmark of cancer, we are evaluating potential enzymatic targets that could mediate the observed effects. To this end, we first evaluated parameters that are often dysregulated in

tumor cells and that are linked to metabolic alterations. A parameter considered was the Extracellular Acidification Rate (ECAR). In cancer cells, ECAR refers to the rate at which the extracellular environment surrounding cancer cells becomes acidic due to the release of metabolic acidic byproducts, mainly lactic acid, from the metabolism of glucose through glycolysis. For that reason, ECAR is a critical indicator of a cell's glycolytic activity and its contribution to the tumor microenvironment's acidity.

First of all, we optimized the method because the test is very sensitive and significant variations between samples greatly affect the significance of the data. Testing different concentrations of PWE, we observed that the treatment significantly alters the ECAR. These results indicate that PWE has an effect on cytosolic metabolism, particularly on glycolysis and lactic acid production in liver cancer cells. To strengthen the data obtained, the Oxygen Consumption Rate (OCR) was also evaluated. OCR, in the context of cancer cells, refers to the measurement of how much oxygen a cell consumes in a given time. This measurement is essential because it reflects the energetic metabolism of cancer cells. Specifically, OCR is related to the dependence on mitochondrial respiration for ATP production.

Liver cancer cells, like many cancer cells exhibit a metabolic shift, relying more on glycolysis, even in the presence of oxygen, which is different from normal cells. These considerations make the evaluation of OCR in our experimental conditions very useful. When we tested the effect of PWE on OCR, we observed a significant modulation at different concentrations and in all the cell lines analyzed. By cross-referencing ECAR and OCR data, we can argue that PWE affects the energetic metabolism of liver cancer cells. Therefore, we focused on specific metabolic target. Among the metabolic enzymes potentially regulated by PWE we have focused on the ME1 since we have already identified it as target of PWE in activated macrophages. However, both the data of western blotting and enzymatic assay indicate a low dependence of ME1 on treatment. We then investigated the second enzyme identified in LPS-induced macrophages, namely GDH. In this case, we obtained a strong inhibition of GDH activity in the presence of PWE.

Figure 2. PWE inhibition of GDH1 activity.

The enzymatic activity was tested with different concentrations of the extract. Protein quantification of GDH through western blotting experiments was also affected by PWE treatment. Moreover, quantitative Real-time PCR assay highlighted an effect of the extract on GDH RNA levels. Therefore, it is possible that the effect observed in liver cancer cells could be mediated by GDH. However, the molecular mechanisms could be multiple since our data highlight both a direct effect on the enzyme and an indirect effect through the regulation of the gene expression. Understanding how GDH gene expression is regulated requires further investigation that will be carried out in the coming months. At present, the analysis of the human *GDH* gene promoter has been performed using the TRANSCACT software. In this way, binding sites for transcription factors potentially involved in the liver cancer cells have been identified. A selection of these transcription factors has been performed and chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP) experiments are underway. To this end, by using the Oligo Analysis Tool Eurofins Genomics, oligonucleotides were designated for ChIP assays by quantitative PCR. We have then demonstrated the involvement of hGDH1 in the proliferation and growth of iCCA cancer cells, and how its modulation through PWE could represent one step towards the development of metabolic therapeutic strategies. Moreover, the use of PWE aligns with a sustainable approach based on circular economy principles, offering a possible solution to the environmental challenges posed by the large-scale generation of this waste. Indeed, pomegranate juice extraction produces inedible by-products, such as peels and seeds, which represent 54% of the fruit's total weight. Therefore, this study supports the sustainable and intensive use of this by-product

CONCLUSION

The potential of three different Aglianico grape pomace, a by-product of the wine supply chain, as a sustainable source of bioactive compounds with antioxidant and anti-proliferative properties has been explored. Our results demonstrated that DIG emerged as the most effective technique, particularly for Barile grape pomace extracts, which exhibited high cytotoxicity against HepG2 cancer cells, exerting a pro-oxidant effect, sparing non-tumor hepatic cells. These findings suggest that DIG could be a cost-effective and industrially scalable method for producing high-value bioactive extracts.

The studies on pomegranate waste focused on investigation on the ethanolic extract, evaluating its activity as antiproliferative agent and its anticancer effect on liver cancer cells.

These studies highlight the potential of these extracts for their application in nutraceutical and pharmaceutical fields, contributing to the valorization of agro-industrial by-products.